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**THE CASABLANCA STOCK EXCHANGE
FACING INFORMATIONAL EFFICIENCY:
EMPIRICAL TESTS & BEHAVIOURAL
ANALYSIS**

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Introduction

The informational efficiency of financial markets lies at the heart of modern finance, yet it remains particularly debated when applied to emerging markets. The Casablanca Stock Exchange is no exception: it mobilises national savings, supports corporate financing, and acts as a key signal for investors, while remaining exposed to structural weaknesses (low liquidity, sectoral concentration, information asymmetries) and to investor behaviour that sometimes departs from perfect rationality.

This thesis sits at the intersection between the theoretical efficiency model developed by Samuelson (1965) and Fama (1970) and the more recent insights of behavioural finance and the Adaptive Markets Hypothesis (Lo, 2004). It pursues a dual objective. First, to rigorously evaluate the degree of efficiency of the Casablanca Stock Exchange—primarily in its weak form—using econometric tests applied to the MASI index (the Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) test for stationarity, the Ljung–Box test for serial independence, and the GARCH model for conditional volatility). Second, to interpret the deviations from classical theory in light of cognitive biases, information asymmetry, and market microstructure, particularly during crisis periods (2008, Covid-19).

The guiding research question is: *To what extent does the Casablanca Stock Exchange satisfy the principles of informational efficiency, and how does taking into account the actual behaviour of investors help explain the deviations observed through empirical tests?*

Beyond the academic contribution, the ambition is to provide institutional actors—notably the Moroccan Capital Market Authority (AMMC) and the Casablanca Stock Exchange itself—with a nuanced perspective. The issue is no longer simply whether the Moroccan market is “efficient or not”, but rather under what conditions it can become so, where its zones of fragility lie, and which levers—whether regulatory, informational, or educational—can strengthen a more adaptive and robust form of efficiency.

Literature Review

A. Theoretical Foundations of Market Efficiency

The theory of informational efficiency rests on the idea that markets instantaneously incorporate all available information. Samuelson (1965) shows that under rational expectations, the dynamics of returns behave as a random walk. Formally:

$$R_{t+1} = \mathbb{E}(R_{t+1} \mid \Omega_t) + u_{t+1} \tag{1}$$

where u_{t+1} is white noise and Ω_t is the information set available at time t , making it impossible to generate persistently abnormal returns through any strategy. Fama (1970) structures this framework into three forms of efficiency (weak, semi-strong, strong) according to the nature of the information incorporated.

However, the empirical literature provides results incompatible with a pure random walk. Lo & MacKinlay (1999) show that under weak-form efficiency, returns should satisfy:

$$\text{Cov}(R_t, R_{t-k}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

That is, they should display no autocovariance. The Variance Ratio (VR) tests this precisely. If returns are independent, the cumulative variance over q periods must grow proportionally to q , implying $VR(q) = 1$. In practice, Lo & MacKinlay frequently find $VR(q) \neq 1$, revealing dependence among returns—often in the form of positive or negative autocorrelations—and therefore short-term predictability incompatible with a strict random walk.

In this context, Jefferis & Smith (2005) apply an evolving efficiency test to Morocco using a GARCH(1,1) model useful for capturing conditional volatility. The specification is:

$$r_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 r_{t-1} + u_t \quad (3)$$

where β_1 measures the instantaneous predictability of the market. Weak-form efficiency implies $\beta_1 = 0$. Their estimates show that between 1995 and 1999, β_1 was largely positive (up to 0.568), revealing strong dependence on past returns and thus marked inefficiency. From mid-1999 onward, β_1 becomes statistically zero, suggesting a progressive convergence towards weak-form efficiency, consistent with the structural modernisation reforms of the late 1990s.

B. Informational Efficiency at the Casablanca Stock Exchange

Analyses applied to the Casablanca Stock Exchange converge on a common finding: the Moroccan market exhibits weak, but incomplete, efficiency. El Khattab & Moudine (2014) identify, via an ARIMA model, persistent predictability in the MASI series. The predictability detected in the MASI means that its variations do not fully follow a random walk, suggesting that some past information retains explanatory power—partially contradicting weak-form efficiency.

More recent findings confirm this trend. Ibenrissoul & Aouragh (2023), covering a period marked by several shocks (the 2008 crisis, the 2013 MSCI downgrading, Covid-19), show that MASI returns remain autocorrelated and non-normal, reflecting a gradual rather

than instantaneous incorporation of information. Lekhal El Oubani (2021) highlight an alternation between phases of relative efficiency and periods of instability, suggesting that the Casablanca Stock Exchange does not follow a permanent regime but oscillates according to economic and institutional conditions—fully in line with the adaptive markets logic.

In summary, the literature agrees on a partially efficient Casablanca Stock Exchange, influenced by liquidity, market concentration, reforms, and investor behaviour.

C. Contributions of Behavioural Finance and Adaptive Markets

The limitations of the efficiency hypothesis have driven the growth of behavioural finance, which explicitly introduces psychology into the analysis of financial decisions. Kahneman Tversky (1979) show that individuals systematically deviate from perfect rationality: loss aversion, overconfidence, and herding behaviour influence their decisions. Agents also use heuristics—mental shortcuts enabling fast but sometimes biased decisions. In finance, these heuristics lead to overweighting certain information, ignoring others, or reacting excessively to news.

Several studies on the Casablanca Stock Exchange (El Khattab Moudine, 2014; Ibenrissoul Aouragh, 2023) confirm the presence of such behaviours: excessive reactions to announcements, low diversification, herding, and amplified volatility. To move beyond the opposition between rationality and psychology, Lo (2004) proposes the Adaptive Markets Hypothesis (AMH), arguing that a market can be efficient at some moments and inefficient at others, depending on competitive pressure, investor learning, and the macroeconomic context.

1. Conceptual and Theoretical Framework: Efficiency, Behaviour, and Information Asymmetry

1.1. The Theory of Market Efficiency: A Rational Ideal Confronted with Facts

The theory of informational efficiency postulates that, in a competitive market composed of rational agents, financial prices constitute the best available estimates of the fundamental value of assets. This intuition, formulated by Samuelson (1965), finds a precise analytical foundation: if investors form rational expectations and use all available information Ω_t , then prices follow a martingale, meaning the current price already incorporates all the predictable part of the future price:

$$\mathbb{E}(P_{t+1} | \Omega_t) = P_t \quad (4)$$

By decomposition, the price dynamics can then be written as:

$$P_{t+1} = P_t + \varepsilon_{t+1}, \quad \mathbb{E}(\varepsilon_{t+1} | \Omega_t) = 0 \quad (5)$$

where ε_{t+1} is an unpredictable shock. Price changes are orthogonal to past information, and returns satisfy:

$$R_{t+1} = \mathbb{E}(R_{t+1} | \Omega_t) + u_{t+1}, \quad \mathbb{E}(u_{t+1} | \Omega_t) = 0 \quad (6)$$

This property implies the unpredictability of returns: no strategy based solely on past data can generate persistently abnormal returns.

Fama (1970) then distinguishes three degrees of efficiency structured around the nature of the information contained in Ω_t :

1. **Weak form:** Prices reflect only information contained in the history of prices and volumes ($I_t = I_t^{\text{past}}$). Weak-form efficiency requires the absence of autocorrelation in returns; the null hypothesis is:

$$\rho_k = \frac{\text{Cov}(R_t, R_{t-k})}{\sigma^2(R_t)} \approx 0, \quad k \neq 0 \quad (7)$$

A significant ρ_k indicates that past returns predict future returns, invalidating weak-form efficiency.

2. **Semi-strong form:** Prices incorporate all publicly available information ($I_t = I_t^{\text{public}}$). Efficiency is verified when cumulative abnormal returns (CAR) show no significant dynamics after the announcement:

$$\text{CAR}(t_1, t_2) = \sum_{t=t_1}^{t_2} AR_t, \quad AR_t = R_t - \mathbb{E}[R_t] \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbb{E}[R_t]$ is the return predicted by an equilibrium model.

3. **Strong form:** Prices reflect all information, including private information ($I_t = I_t^{\text{private}}$). For an informed investor:

$$AR_t^* = R_t - \mathbb{E}[R_t | I_t^*] \quad (9)$$

Under strong-form efficiency, even conditioning on private information, the investor should not obtain persistently abnormal returns:

$$\mathbb{E}(AR_t^*) = 0 \quad (10)$$

This theoretical architecture is coherent but does not hold up well to empirical scrutiny. Engle (1982) and Hamilton (1994) show that financial series display conditional heteroskedasticity, incompatible with the classical random walk. The variance of the shock does not appear constant but depends on past information:

$$\text{Var}(u_t | \Omega_t) = \sigma_t^2 \neq \sigma^2 \quad (11)$$

This phenomenon, known as *volatility clustering*, constitutes a major violation of the classical model.

1.2. Beyond Rationality: Behavioural Finance and Information Asymmetry

Kahneman Tversky (1979) introduced Prospect Theory, which does not reject standard economics but complements it. It shows that individuals use mental shortcuts, sometimes react emotionally, and possess bounded rationality. Several biases influence financial decisions:

- **Overconfidence:** investors overestimate their own abilities.
- **Loss aversion:** investors are more sensitive to losses than to equivalent gains.
- **Disposition effect:** tendency to sell winning positions too early but retain losing ones.
- **Herding:** collective imitation that fuels bubbles Kahneman, 2011.

Informational asymmetry also plays a central role. El Bouazizi (2018), studying listed companies in Casablanca between 2005 and 2014, shows that firm size, stock performance, and regulatory scrutiny significantly influence the degree of asymmetry, and that stronger institutional oversight and accounting transparency directly improve market efficiency.

2. Empirical Assessment of MASI Efficiency

2.1. SWOT Analysis: The Casablanca Stock Exchange between Regulatory Strength and Structural Constraints

2.1.1. Strengths: A Solid and Well-Regulated Market Infrastructure

The Casablanca Stock Exchange's strengths lie primarily in the establishment of an institutionally robust market framework and continuous modernisation of practices. The main strength is the stability of the institutional framework ensured by the Moroccan Capital Market Authority (AMMC), which rigorously oversees financial intermediaries around the pillars of investor protection, transparency, and surveillance. The adoption of IFRS and the progressive integration of ESG reporting oblige issuers to greater discipline, aligning the Moroccan market with international standards. The dematerialisation of securities and the use of centralised electronic platforms for settlement and delivery also increase operational efficiency and reduce friction.

Regarding diversification, the development of UCITS (Undertakings for Collective Investment in Transferable Securities) and the progress of securitisation modestly broaden financing channels. The single Sukuk issuance in 2018 (1 billion dirhams), although a marker of openness to participatory finance, illustrates that this segment remains embryonic. Finally, the recent revival of IPOs (Vicenne, Cash Plus, SGTM) signals a return of corporate confidence in the stock exchange as a viable source of equity financing.

2.1.2. Weaknesses: Concentration and Informational Inefficiency

The Casablanca Stock Exchange suffers from structural weaknesses that limit its development and reduce its efficiency. The market remains highly concentrated: in the first half of 2025, four capitalisations (Attijariwafa Bank, Itissalat Al-Maghrib, SODEP-Marsa Maroc, MANAGEM) alone formed nearly 40% of total market capitalisation Casablanca Stock Exchange, 2025. Banks alone represented approximately 31% of the market.

This concentration is aggravated by a very limited supply of securities, with fewer than eighty listed companies. This scarcity is a direct brake on market liquidity, reinforcing the concentration of trading on the few "blue chips" and leaving other securities in chronic under-liquidity—discouraging institutional investors who need rapid exit capacity for large volumes.

Moreover, information asymmetry, confirmed by El Bouazizi (2018), constitutes a non-negligible market cost. The study shows that asymmetry, measured by the bid-ask

spread, is inversely correlated with size, liquidity, and regulatory oversight, meaning that the cost of information is higher for small-cap or thinly traded securities.

2.1.3. Opportunities: Regional Leverage and Accelerated Digitalisation

The Vision 2035, as defined in the New Development Model (CSMD), 2021, constitutes the national reference framework to guide long-term public policy. The report describes an ambition for economic transformation based on three priorities: accelerating structural transformation, improving financing mechanisms, and elevating governance and regulatory standards. These orientations create a favourable environment for the development of the capital market.

Casablanca Finance City (CFC) consolidates Morocco's positioning as a regional financial hub: its 2023 activity report lists 202 member companies operating in more than 50 African countries. The AMMC's new Business Intelligence platform also automates the collection, control, and analysis of market data (AMMC, 2023), reducing information asymmetries. The rise of AI and Big Data offers significant potential to increase liquidity and strengthen market integrity.

2.1.4. Threats: Low Financial Culture and Regional Competition

Low financial literacy and households' marked preference for non-stock savings constitute a fundamental threat, limiting the development of the retail investor base. Several issuers have also failed to meet disclosure obligations in recent years: the AMMC's 2019 annual report notes persistent delays in publishing financial statements for Ciments du Maroc, Ennakl Automobiles, and Stroc Industries, as well as incomplete disclosures for Crédit Agricole du Maroc, and 16 issuers failing to publish quarterly indicators in Q2 2019 (AMMC, 2019).

Finally, regional competition is intensifying: Johannesburg, Lagos, and Nairobi are rapidly modernising their market infrastructures and diversifying their instruments, increasing their relative attractiveness.

2.2. Empirical Tests of Efficiency

2.2.1. Random Walk Test

The objective of this subsection is to verify the weak form of informational efficiency on the Casablanca Stock Exchange by testing whether the price and return of the MASI index follow a random walk process. This analysis relies on two econometric tests most commonly used in the literature : the ADF test and the Ljung–Box test.

Figure 1: Evolution of prices and daily returns of the MASI index, 2005–2025.

Source: Author (personal processing).

Source: Author (personal processing).

The prices display a trajectory marked by successive bull and bear cycles, with pronounced volatility episodes, notably during the 2008 financial crisis, the 2020 pandemic, and recent adjustments in 2025. Returns oscillate around zero, erratically and without persistent trend. They are calculated using the standard logarithmic formula:

$$r_t = 100 \times [\ln(P_t) - \ln(P_{t-1})] \quad (12)$$

This method stabilises variance and more faithfully captures successive information adjustments. The contrast between the non-stationarity of prices and the stationarity of returns suggests dynamics compatible with a random walk—the key condition for weak-form informational efficiency.

Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) Test The ADF test determines whether a time series is stationary or non-stationary, i.e., whether it contains a unit root. Methodologically, the test is derived from the basic autoregressive model:

$$P_t = a P_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (13)$$

If $a = 1$, the series is non-stationary. Rewriting in differences:

$$\Delta P_t = (a - 1)P_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (14)$$

Setting $\gamma = a - 1$, the augmented specification estimated in the ADF test is:

$$\Delta P_t = \gamma P_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i \Delta P_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (15)$$

where β_i terms absorb residual autocorrelation in order for the estimate of γ to be valid. The hypotheses are:

$$H_0 : \gamma = 0 \quad (\text{unit root, non-stationary series}) \quad (16)$$

$$H_1 : \gamma < 0 \quad (\text{stationary series}) \quad (17)$$

Table 1: ADF Test on MASI Prices (2005–2025)

Series	ADF Statistic	p-value	Conclusion
Price (close)	−2.344	0.4327	Non-stationary (unit root present)

Source: Author (personal processing).

The ADF test applied to the MASI closing price series shows a p-value of 0.4327, above the 5% threshold, indicating that the series is non-stationary. The null hypothesis of a unit root cannot be rejected: the autoregressive coefficient is statistically indistinguishable from 1, implying that prices do not revert to a stable mean and that each shock has a lasting effect. MASI prices therefore follow a random walk process, consistent with Samuelson (1965) and Fama (1970).

Table 2: ADF Test on MASI Returns (2005–2025)

Series	p-value	Conclusion
Returns (ret)	< 0.01	Stationary

Source: Author (personal processing).

The ADF test applied to daily returns reveals a p-value below 0.01: the null hypothesis of a unit root is rejected. Returns revert around a stable mean and display no lasting memory effect. Prices are non-stationary but returns are stationary, confirming the random walk in prices and supporting the validity of weak-form efficiency.

Ljung–Box Test The Ljung–Box test examines the existence of global autocorrelations in returns. Its principle consists in verifying whether several autocorrelation coefficients are simultaneously zero. Methodologically, the test rests on a Q statistic that aggregates autocorrelations up to a certain number of lags:

$$Q = n(n + 2) \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\hat{\rho}_k^2}{n - k} \quad (18)$$

where n is the sample size and $\hat{\rho}_k$ is the sample autocorrelation at lag k . Under H_0 , Q follows a χ^2 distribution with m degrees of freedom.

- H_0 : no autocorrelation \Rightarrow efficient market.
- H_1 : autocorrelation present \Rightarrow short-term inefficiency.

Table 3: Ljung–Box Test Results on MASI Returns (2005–2025)

Lags	χ^2 Statistic	d.f.	p-value	Conclusion
10	291.44	10	2.2×10^{-16}	Reject $H_0 \rightarrow$ Autocorrelation present
20	314.42	20	2.2×10^{-16}	Reject $H_0 \rightarrow$ Autocorrelation present

Source: Author (personal processing).

The results indicate a very low p-value for lags 10 and 20, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation. This translates into significant serial dependence among successive MASI returns, suggesting imperfect efficiency in the short run. This partial predictability can be explained by low market liquidity, delays in information dissemination, or mimetic and emotional investor behaviour (Kahneman, 2011).

Interpretation and Conclusion The set of econometric tests reveals a Casablanca Stock Exchange that is broadly efficient but marked by certain temporary inefficiencies. Prices follow a random walk and returns are stationary, validating weak-form efficiency. However, the presence of weak but significant global autocorrelations highlights non-rational behaviours or market frictions capable of creating transient deviations from perfect efficiency theory.

The degree of efficiency varies according to economic conditions and agent behaviour, in agreement with the Adaptive Markets Hypothesis proposed by Lo (2004).

2.2.2. GARCH(1,1) Model — Conditional Volatility

To model the evolution of MASI volatility, the GARCH(1,1) model Bollerslev, 1986, building on Engle (1982), assumes that the conditional variance of returns depends both on recent shocks and on past volatility. The model equation is:

$$h_t = \omega + \alpha \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta h_{t-1} \quad (19)$$

where:

- h_t is the conditional variance at time t ;
- ω is a positive constant representing the baseline volatility level;
- α measures the market's immediate reaction to new shocks (information effect);
- β captures the persistence or memory of past volatility;
- ε_{t-1}^2 is the squared shock from the previous period.

When $\alpha + \beta < 1$, volatility is stationary: the market absorbs information shocks quickly. When $\alpha + \beta$ is close to 1, volatility persistence is high, indicating slow assimilation of information and thus potential market inefficiency.

Table 4: GARCH(1,1) Results on the MASI (2005–2025)

Parameter	Economic Interpretation	Estimated Value
α (alpha)	Immediate market reaction to recent shocks (impact of new information)	0.2533
β (beta)	Persistence or memory of past volatility	0.6836
$\alpha + \beta$	Overall persistence of conditional volatility	0.9368
Half-life (days)	Average time for a shock's effect to halve	10.62

Source: Author (personal processing).

These estimates show that 25% of current volatility stems directly from recent shocks, while 68% results from past volatility. The high sum ($\alpha + \beta = 0.9368$) reflects strong persistence, confirmed by a half-life of approximately ten days. On an economic level, these results reveal that the Casablanca Stock Exchange reacts to new information but that the full price adjustment occurs gradually—in line with the conclusions of Jefferis Smith (2005) and Lekhal El Oubani (2021).

3. The Contribution of Behavioural Finance

3.1. Investor Typology and Dominant Behaviours

Investors present on the Casablanca Stock Exchange do not act homogeneously. In 2024, Moroccan legal entities and UCITS alone concentrated 64% of the volume traded on the central market, against 25% for individual investors and only 5% for foreign investors AMMC, 2024.

Institutional investors. Despite their sophistication, institutional investors remain exposed to reputational risk and may adopt mimetic strategies to avoid relative under-performance. By converging on the same arbitrage, they reduce informational diversity—particularly relevant in a market where liquidity remains limited (12.45% in 2024, its highest level since 2011).

Individual investors. Retail participants represent a limited share of capitalisation but contribute significantly to volatility, especially for illiquid securities. Their behaviour is marked by recurring biases: overconfidence, the disposition effect (rapid realisation of gains, retention of losses), and sensitivity to rumours.

Foreign investors. Foreign investors held 24.1% of total market capitalisation and 8.2% of free-float capitalisation in 2024, but only 5% of the volume traded on the central market AMMC, 2024.

3.2. Manifestations of Behavioural Biases on the Casablanca Stock Exchange

Overconfidence and overreaction. Overconfidence manifests when investors overestimate the precision of their forecasts or over-interpret incomplete signals. In a market where fundamental information is sometimes insufficiently disseminated, these behaviours lead to overreaction or underreaction to news, followed by correction phases.

Loss aversion. A central component of Prospect Theory Kahneman Tversky, 1979, loss aversion contributes to delaying price adjustments to new information, slowing adjustments, and contributing to the volatility persistence evidenced by the GARCH model, particularly during stress or uncertainty.

Herding. Mimicry appears frequently in markets characterised by high information asymmetry, as is the case for the Casablanca Stock Exchange. Investors tend to reproduce behaviours observed in other actors rather than relying solely on their own analyses. This amplifies upward or downward movements, sometimes independently of economic fundamentals.

3.3. Case Studies: Casablanca Stock Exchange Reactions during Crisis Periods

The analysis of MASI efficiency gains in precision when observed during crises. The 2008 and Covid-19 episodes function as real-world tests where the speed of market adjustment becomes more visible. For each crisis, returns are divided into three sequences—pre-crisis, crisis, post-crisis—to track the evolution of volatility and predictability. The ADF and GARCH(1,1) tests are re-applied on these narrow windows:

- **ADF:** evaluates the random walk; a low p-value signals predictability, i.e., greater inefficiency.
- **GARCH(1,1):** captures the immediate reaction to shocks (α) and the persistence of volatility (β). The key point lies in $\alpha + \beta$: the closer this sum is to 1, the more volatility persists and the more slowly information diffuses.

Table 5: Test Results Before / During / After the Crises

Crisis	Phase	ADF Test		GARCH(1,1) Model		
		Volatility (sd)	p-value	α	β	$\alpha + \beta$
2008	Pre-crisis	0.00993	0.01	0.2988	0.6977	0.9965
2008	Crisis	0.00995	0.01	0.2118	0.7126	0.9244
2008	Post-crisis	0.00689	0.01	0.3141	0.4038	0.7180
Covid-19	Pre-crisis	0.00568	0.01	0.1983	0.5680	0.7663
Covid-19	Crisis	0.00963	0.01	0.1664	0.7871	0.9535
Covid-19	Post-crisis	0.00708	0.01	0.4237	0.4751	0.8989

Source: Author (personal processing).

The two crises display distinct behaviours. For 2008, volatility was already highly persistent before the shock ($\alpha + \beta \approx 0.997$), suggesting a tense market sensitive to negative signals. The post-crisis period shows progressive stabilisation. Covid-19 produces a different dynamic: persistence rises rapidly at the onset of the crisis ($\alpha + \beta \approx 0.95$), reflecting a sudden, global shock that is difficult to absorb. Even after the crisis, this persistence remains elevated, as if health uncertainty had left a lasting imprint on expectations. In both cases, low ADF p-values indicate increased predictability of returns, typical of stress phases.

3.4. Limits and Complementarity with Efficiency Theory

Behavioural finance does not overturn the efficiency hypothesis; it specifies its vulnerable zones. Cognitive biases, emotions, and herding emerge primarily when information circulates poorly or when the market is under stress. On the methodological side, the analysis remains constrained by the absence of direct behavioural data: biases must be inferred from proxies—conditional volatility, autocorrelations, or asymmetries extracted from the GARCH model.

General Conclusion

The analysis conducted in this thesis shows that the Casablanca Stock Exchange occupies an intermediate zone: it tends towards weak-form informational efficiency without reaching the ideal of a perfectly efficient market. The random walk tests (ADF), serial dependence tests (Ljung–Box), and GARCH(1,1) models indicate that, over the period studied, MASI prices follow dynamics broadly compatible with weak-form

efficiency, but that recurrent pockets of inefficiency persist: residual autocorrelations, high volatility persistence, and slow adjustment to shocks. These fragilities intensify during crisis periods, when volatility explodes and shock memory lengthens.

The literature on the Moroccan market El Khattab Moudine, 2014; Lekhal El Oubani, 2021; Ibenrissoul Aouragh, 2023 converges with these results: the market appears semi-efficient in the empirical sense and adaptive in the sense of Lo (2004), where the degree of efficiency fluctuates according to market conditions, liquidity, and investor structure. Behavioural finance gives meaning to these findings: overconfidence, loss aversion, herding, and information asymmetry contribute to the formation of price anomalies and the persistence of elevated volatility.

Behavioural finance does not replace efficiency theory; it completes it. The Adaptive Markets Hypothesis offers a relevant framework for reading the trajectory of the Casablanca Stock Exchange: efficiency appears as a process, not a state. For regulators and operators, the challenges are clear: strengthen transparency, improve the quality and dissemination of information, develop financial education, and take behavioural biases into account in regulation. It is under these conditions that the Casablanca Stock Exchange can move closer to an efficiency that genuinely serves the financing of the Moroccan economy.

Looking ahead, the future impact of digitalisation, fintech, and artificial intelligence constitutes a decisive lever. The growth of digital trading platforms, automated data analysis, anomaly detection tools deployed by the AMMC, the gradual introduction of tokenisation, and the rise of open finance are all likely to reduce information asymmetries, increase liquidity, and strengthen market discipline.

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Ljung–Box Test — Methodological Details

The Ljung–Box test Kahneman, 2011 verifies the existence of global autocorrelations in a time series. It evaluates whether successive returns evolve independently (efficient market) or exhibit serial dependence (short-term inefficiency).

- H_0 : no autocorrelation \rightarrow random returns \rightarrow efficient market.
- H_1 : autocorrelation present \rightarrow serial dependence \rightarrow short-term inefficiency.

The test statistic is:

$$Q = n(n + 2) \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\hat{\rho}_k^2}{n - k} \quad (20)$$

where n is the sample size and $\hat{\rho}_k$ the autocorrelation coefficient at lag k . Under H_0 , $Q \sim \chi^2(m)$.

Appendix 2: R Code for ADF and Ljung–Box Tests

Listing 1: ADF and Ljung-Box tests on MASI data

```

1 # Packages
2 pkgs <- c("readr", "dplyr", "lubridate", "ggplot2", "tseries")
3 new <- pkgs[!pkgs %in% installed.packages()[, "Package"]]
4 if (length(new)) install.packages(new, quiet = TRUE)
5 invisible(lapply(pkgs, library, character.only = TRUE))
6
7 # Data
8 masi <- read_csv("MASI_depuis_2005.csv", show_col_types = FALSE) %>%
9   select(Date, Price) %>%
10  mutate(
11    date = lubridate::mdy(Date),
12    Price = as.character(Price),
13    close = readr::parse_number(Price)
14  ) %>%
15  arrange(date) %>%
16  filter(!is.na(close)) %>%
17  select(date, close)
18
19 # Log returns (%)
20 masi <- masi %>%
21  mutate(ret = 100 * (log(close) - log(dplyr::lag(close)))) %>%
22  filter(!is.na(ret))
23

```

```

24 # ADF on prices
25 adf.test(masi$close)
26
27 # ADF on returns
28 adf.test(masi$ret)
29
30 # Ljung-Box test
31 Box.test(masi$ret, lag = 10, type = "Ljung-Box")
32 Box.test(masi$ret, lag = 20, type = "Ljung-Box")

```

Appendix 3: GARCH(1,1) Model — Methodological Details

The GARCH(1,1) model Bollerslev, 1986 decomposes returns as follows:

$$r_t = \mu + \varepsilon_t, \quad \varepsilon_t = z_t \sqrt{h_t}, \quad z_t \sim N(0, 1) \quad (21)$$

The conditional variance evolves according to:

$$h_t = \omega + \alpha \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta h_{t-1} \quad (22)$$

The model is stationary if $\alpha + \beta < 1$. The half-life is calculated as:

$$\text{Half-life} = \frac{\ln(0.5)}{\ln(\alpha + \beta)} \quad (23)$$

The reactivity ratio $\alpha/(\alpha + \beta)$ indicates the share of volatility attributable to recent shocks. For the MASI, this ratio is approximately 0.20, meaning volatility depends primarily on the past rather than on new information.

Table 6: Economic Interpretation of GARCH Parameters

Parameter	Statistical Role	Economic Reading
ω	Minimum market volatility	Baseline volatility present even in the absence of a shock, linked to constant factors such as market size, average liquidity, or regulation.
α	Reactivity to new information	Translates the speed of the market's reaction to new information.
β	Memory of past volatility	The higher β , the more periods of high volatility tend to persist.
$\alpha + \beta$	Overall persistence	If close to 1, volatility propagates for a long time before returning to its mean level.

Appendix 4: Complete R Code for GARCH(1,1) Applied to the MASI (2005–2025)

Listing 2: GARCH(1,1) estimation on MASI returns

```

1 # 1) Required packages
2 pkgs <- c("readr", "dplyr", "rugarch", "tseries", "lubridate")
3 to_install <- pkgs[!pkgs %in% installed.packages()[,1]]
4 if(length(to_install)) install.packages(to_install)
5 invisible(lapply(pkgs, library, character.only = TRUE))
6
7 # 2) Import and prepare data
8 masi <- read_csv("MASI_depuis_2005.csv", show_col_types = FALSE) |>
9   select(Date, Price) |>
10  mutate(date = mdy(Date),
11         close = as.numeric(Price)) |>
12  arrange(date) |>
13  mutate(ret = c(NA, diff(log(close)))) |>
14  filter(is.finite(ret))
15
16 # 3) Fast GARCH(1,1) function
17 garch_rapid <- function(x, nom = "Series") {
18   spec <- ugarchspec(
19     variance.model = list(model = "sGARCH", garchOrder = c(1,1)),
20     mean.model      = list(armaOrder = c(0,0), include.mean = TRUE),
21     distribution.model = "std"
22   )
23   fit <- ugarchfit(spec, data = x, solver = "hybrid")
24   coefs <- coef(fit)

```

```

25 a <- coefs["alpha1"]; b <- coefs["beta1"]
26 s <- a + b
27 hl <- if(s > 0 && s < 1) log(0.5) / log(s) else NA
28 z <- residuals(fit, standardize = TRUE)
29 cat(sprintf("\n[%s] alpha=%.4f | beta=%.4f | alpha+beta=%.4f |
30 Half-life ~ %s days\n",
31 nom, a, b, s,
32 ifelse(is.na(hl), "NA", sprintf("%.2f", hl))))
33 invisible(list(fit = fit, alpha = a, beta = b,
34 alpha_beta = s, half_life = hl))
35 }
36
37 # 4) Run test
38 res_masi <- garch_rapid(masi$ret, "MASI")

```

Appendix 5: MASI Efficiency during Crisis Periods — ADF, GARCH(1,1), and Volatility Visualisation

Listing 3: Crisis analysis: ADF + GARCH(1,1) by phase

```

1 library(dplyr); library(tseries); library(rugarch); library(ggplot2)
2
3 # Import and prepare MASI data
4 masi <- read.csv("MASI_depuis_2005.csv", stringsAsFactors = FALSE)
5 masi <- masi %>%
6   mutate(Date = as.Date(Date, format = "%m/%d/%Y"),
7          Price = as.numeric(gsub(",", "", Price))) %>%
8   arrange(Date) %>%
9   mutate(ret = c(NA, diff(log(Price)))) %>%
10  filter(is.finite(ret))
11
12 # Time windows: pre / crisis / post for 2008 and Covid-19
13 per <- data.frame(
14   crise = c("Crise_2008", "Crise_2008", "Crise_2008",
15            "Covid19", "Covid19", "Covid19"),
16   phase = c("pre", "crise", "post", "pre", "crise", "post"),
17   start = as.Date(c("2005-01-01", "2008-01-01", "2010-01-01",
18                    "2015-01-01", "2020-01-01", "2022-01-01")),
19   end = as.Date(c("2007-12-31", "2009-12-31", "2012-12-31",
20                  "2019-12-31", "2021-12-31", max(masi$Date)))
21
22 # Function: ADF + GARCH(1,1) per sub-period
23 estime_periode <- function(d1, d2) {
24   r <- masi$ret[masi$Date >= d1 & masi$Date <= d2]
25   r <- r[is.finite(r)]
26   adf_p <- tryCatch(adf.test(r)$p.value, error = function(e) NA)

```

```
27 spec <- ugarchspec(variance.model = list(model="sGARCH", garchOrder
    =c(1,1)),
28                   mean.model = list(armaOrder=c(0,0), include.mean
    =TRUE),
29                   distribution.model = "norm")
30 fit <- tryCatch(ugarchfit(spec, r, solver="hybrid"), error=
    function(e) NULL)
31 cf <- coef(fit)
32 a <- cf["alpha1"]; b <- cf["beta1"]
33 c(n=length(r), sd=sd(r), adf_p=adf_p, alpha=a, beta=b, alpha_beta=a+
    b)
34 }
35
36 # Collect results
37 res_list <- mapply(estimate_periode, per$start, per$end, SIMPLIFY =
    FALSE)
38 res_tab <- cbind(per, do.call(rbind, res_list))
39 res_tab$phase <- factor(res_tab$phase, levels = c("pre", "crise", "post"
    ))
40
41 # Volatility chart
42 ggplot(res_tab, aes(x = phase, y = sd, fill = crise)) +
43   geom_col(position = "dodge") +
44   labs(x = "Phase", y = "Volatility (standard deviation of returns)",
45        title = "MASI Volatility Before / During / After the 2008 and
46             Covid-19 Crises") +
47   theme_minimal()
```